

STUDIES IN THE BEHAVIOUR OF BI-UNIVALENT SALTS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS. PART XI. BARIUM ACETATE

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From the study of the cells of the type

and the solubility of barium iodate in potassium nitrate and potassium acetate solutions, the dissociation of barium acetate in its aqueous solutions has been determined. Barium acetate has been found to be completely dissociated in its aqueous solutions at least up to a concentration of 0.1 M.

In an earlier communication by Prasad *et al.* (*this Journal*, 1953, 30, 633), barium acetate was assumed to be completely dissociated in its aqueous solutions up to 0.1M. Since barium ion forms complexes with some organic acid anions, the present investigation has been undertaken to test the validity of the earlier assumption.

The cells of the type,

(where 'C' indicates concentration of barium acetate in g. mol. per litre), were studied and the solubility of barium iodate was determined separately in potassium nitrate and potassium acetate solutions of varying concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Barium acetate used was of E. Merck's reagent quality and was recrystallised before use. The stock solution of the salt was prepared in double distilled water and its exact concentration was determined gravimetrically as barium sulphate. The other solutions were prepared from the stock solution by dilution. Pure distilled mercury and chemically precipitated mercurous acetate were used for preparing the electrodes. The cell vessels and the bridge were of the type previously used (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 683).

The E.M.F. was measured with the help of a K-type Leeds-Northrup potentiometer at $35^\circ \pm 0.02^\circ$ in an electrically regulated air thermostat. Duplicate experiments were performed for each combination of half cells and the duplicates agreed within 0.2 mv. The half cells having the same composition were checked against each other. The E.M.F. produced by such a combination was mostly less than 0.1 mv. In cases where it exceeded this limit, the half cells concerned were rejected.

For solubility measurements barium iodate was prepared by precipitation from a solution of barium acetate by the addition of a dilute solution of potassium iodate with constant mechanical stirring. The precipitated sample, after careful washing and drying, was analysed (% Ba expected 27.19; found 27.17). The stock solution of potassium acetate was prepared by mixing calculated amounts of standard acetic acid and potassium hydroxide solutions. The stock solution of potassium nitrate was prepared by weighing the salt. The 0.0, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08 and 0.1 molar solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution.

The solutions containing an excess of barium iodate were shaken in glass-stoppered bottles for about five days on a mechanical shaker and then were allowed to stand for about three days inside an air thermostat at 35°. These periods were found sufficient for the attainment of equilibrium. The solubility was determined by estimating the amount of iodate in the solution phase by titrating with a standard 0.009535*N* thiosulphate solution.

TABLE I

C_1	C_2	E.M.F. (obs.)	E.M.F. (calc.)	C_1	C_2	E.M.F. (obs.)	E.M.F. (calc.)
0.01	0.04	0.03422	0.03380	0.02	0.10	0.03900	0.03856
0.01	0.06	0.04322	0.04350	0.04	0.06	0.00920	0.00770
0.01	0.08	0.05087	0.05030	0.04	0.08	0.01682	0.01650
0.01	0.10	0.05535	0.05560	0.04	0.10	0.02250	0.02180
0.02	0.04	0.01580	0.01677	0.06	0.08	0.00675	0.00680
0.02	0.06	0.02630	0.02646	0.06	0.10	0.04322	0.04350
0.02	0.08	0.03250	0.03331	0.08	0.10	0.00520	0.00535

DISCUSSION

The E.M.F.'s of the cells of the type used above at 35° are shown in the table in all cases except for the combination 0.01*M*, 0.02*M* as reproducible readings could not be obtained in this case. The E.M.F. of the cells may also be calculated from the equation

$$E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{C_1 f_1}{C_2 f_2}$$

where C_1 and C_2 and f_1 and f_2 are respectively the concentrations and the activity coefficients of acetate ions in the two solutions. If barium acetate is assumed to be completely dissociated, the concentration of the acetate ion will be twice the molar concentration of barium acetate. The activity coefficient of acetate ion may be assumed to be the same as that of the chloride ion at the same ionic strength. The calculated E.M.F.'s on the basis of the above assumption are shown in the last column of the table. It is found that the calculated and the observed E.M.F.'s agree within 1 mv in all cases where reproducible readings are available. This clearly indicates that in the

case of barium acetate the dissociation is almost complete within the range of concentrations studied.

FIG. 1

In dilute solutions of barium nitrate we expect complete dissociation on account of the structure of the nitrate ion. If dissociation is incomplete in the case of barium acetate, the solubility of barium iodate in the same concentrations (having the same ionic strength) of potassium nitrate and potassium acetate would become different. The figure given shows that there is hardly any such difference. This further supports the above view that barium acetate is almost completely dissociated in its aqueous solutions up to the concentration of 0.1 M.

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